

Microplastics in terrestrial environments: Reviewing current understanding to determine the positive and negative aspects of soil

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ABSTRACT

Plastic production and disposal have grown to be serious issues for the future of the world. The long lifespan and extensive use of synthetic polymers have contributed to the occurrence of plastic waste in the environment on a global scale. Plastic, which can be found in soils, species that live in and around soil, and adjacent to plants, is a novel stressor. There is very little known about the prevalence of microplastics in terrestrial systems. This paper provides an extensive overview of the current understanding of the causes, manifestations, impact and dangers of microplastic pollution in terrestrial (agricultural) settings.

Keywords: Plastic, Microplastic, Soil, Soil organisms, MPs (micro plastics).

1. Soil

The support for a lot of animal and human activities depends on soil, which is essential for plant growth. The soil serves as a storage area for water as well as nutrients, meeting the needs of the plants throughout their growth and development process. Additionally, the soil may offer a setting for the decomposition and immobilization of substances applied to the surface, such as insecticides, fertilizers, and waste materials including sewage sludge, waste from animals, and composted garbage. The soil is a multifaceted, ever-changing system in which relationships and interactions between the physical, biological, and chemical environments lead to the conversion of materials, potentially making initially hazardous substances less hazardous and immobilizing others as an outcome of these added materials' connections with the organic and inorganic soil components. The interactions and changes could take place over decades or nearly instantly, in the short period between distinct occurrences like rainstorms, in the medium-term spanning months or years (Nortcliff et al., 2006).

2. Soil Microbes

In addition to being crucial for plant growth, nutrition, and health in agro-environments, the rhizosphere microbiome also has an immediate or subsequent effect on the biomass, composition, and performance of plant communities in ecological settings. The composition and structure of the microbial population in the rhizosphere are

primarily influenced by soil characteristics and plant species (Joos & De Tender, 2022). The overall composition of the microbial community and environmental factors (such as temperature, pH, soil moisture, etc.) influence how quickly organic matter decomposes and how quickly nutrients are cycled as a result (Pendall et al., 2004). Plant growth may be facilitated by multitrophic interactions in the rhizosphere and their effects on the above-ground assemblages of mutualists, symbionts, and herbivores (Philippot et al., 2013). When farming practices and environmental disturbances upset the soil system's natural balance, these organisms frequently become disturbed (Joos & De Tender, 2022).

3. Plastic As A Danger To Soil

Plastic, which exists in soils, around organisms that live in them, and near to plants, is a novel stressor. Normally plastics are very popular for the production of a huge variety of items as they are lightweight, sturdy, long-lasting, and affordable. These very same characteristics also make plastics a significant environmental threat (Laist, 1987). The sizes of plastic debris are generally categorized as follows: mega-debris (>100 mm), macro-debris (>20 mm), meso-debris (20-5 mm), and micro-debris (>5 mm) (Barnes et al., 2009). 'Nano plastics' will eventually develop when plastic fragments in the environment continue to break down and get smaller size (Koelmans et al., 2015). Due to the fact that hundreds of millions of

tonnes of plastic are produced each year for public use, part of it is released into the environment, it is extremely difficult to understand the sources, abundance, and composition of microplastics that exist in the environment. It is estimated that 4-23 times as much plastic is released annually to land than to oceans. (Horton et al., 2017).

4. Sources Of Plastic In Soil

MPs are mostly produced by automobiles tire wear, home and laundry dirt, industrial operations (e.g., plastic blasting and deflating), and degradation of surfaces made of or covered with plastic, such as artificial turf and polymeric paint. The size and density of the particles affect how well MP is retained. During primary and secondary treatment, sewage sludge almost entirely retains MPs with a density larger than water. Oversized floating particles are successfully removed by final filtration, but smaller, lighter particles are naturally liberated with wastewater effluents. Sewage sludge used as fertilizer for agricultural purposes in soil might have more (micro) plastics compared to marine basins (Nizzetto et al., 2016). An annual usage of sludge to agricultural land can result in two or three times increases in MP content in the soil. (Van den Berg et al., 2020). Plastic mulching and plastic fertilizer additives are purposeful soil contaminators, whereas composts, fermented organic waste products, sewage sludge, and irrigation with water from polluted lakes or rivers are inadvertent (Joos & De Tender, 2022).

5. Soil Organisms Behave In Presence Of Micro Plastic

Earthworms are an ideal species to test for analysing the pollution and effects of MPs on soil ecosystems because they may absorb little plastics and produce secondary MPs inside of their bodies. A recent soil study found that earthworms of the species *Lumbricus terrestris* that were exposed to polyethylene particles died at rates of 8% at 450 g kg⁻¹ and 25% at 600 g kg⁻¹ polyethylene concentrations. Additionally, they found decreased growth and detrimental impacts

on the development of burrows (Huerta Lwanga et al., 2016). According to a different study using the species *Eisenia Andrei*, MPs had an impact on the histopathological harm and immune responses of earthworms rather than their survival, growth, and reproduction. The earthworms' middle digestive tract and gut both contained MPs (Rodriguez-Seijo et al., 2017). Plastic residues and MPs can alter the diversity of various bacterial phyla and families in soil microbes, however the consequences varied depending on the type of bacteria. The soil's total nitrogen content, dissolved organic carbon content, and soil moisture front vertical and horizontal accessibility can all be reduced by 14%, 10%, 9%, and 7%, respectively, by residues of plastic and MPs. In the presence of plastic wastes and MPs, plant height and root biomass reduced by 13% and 14%, respectively, while soil animals' body masses and reproduction rates reduced by 5% and 11%, respectively. However, in the presence of MPs and plastic residues, soil enzyme activity increased by 7% to 441% (Zhang et al., 2022).

6. Negative Impact And Risks Of Plastic Present In Soil

MPs alters the physical and chemical properties of soil by (1) decreasing soil bulk density, (2) modifying water availability, (3) enhancing soil pH, and (4) increasing dissolved organic matter (Joos & De Tender, 2022). Widespread manmade pollutants known as microplastics (MPs) damage the terrestrial environment and act as carriers for other pollutants. According to the study, environmental factors including culture temperature had a negative correlation with the fungi's ability to break down MPs (You et al., 2022). Due to the material's slow rate of decomposition, plastic particles contain a significant amount of carbon, the most of which will be relatively inert. The very broad C: N ratio of this substance will eventually cause microbial immobilization as it slowly degrades over time (Rillig, 2018)

Microplastic type	Major hypothesized effect pathway	Expected effect size and direction (+, -) for plant growth	Potential concern for food safety (in an agricultural context)
Biodegradable	Nutrient immobilization in soil (short-term)	Intermediate (-)	Decreased nutrient contents
Nanoplastic	Toxicity to plant roots and soil microbiota	Minimal to intermediate (-)	Plastic ingestion (uptake), especially for consumed belowground plant portions

Source: (Rillig et al., 2019)

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